

Classical Entropy from Correspondence Principle and Quantum Entropy

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The correspondence principle is used to link quantum high energy spatial density to classical spatial density $C/v(x)$ where $.5mv(x)v(x)+V(x)=E$. This density is then often used to calculate Shannon's entropy of the form $-\text{density} \ln(\text{density})$ as in (1). In this note, we formulate classical entropy in a different manner and obtain the expression: $S \text{ density} = -\sum_i n(i)\ln(n(i)) - (1-n(i))\ln(1-n(i))$ where $n(i)=P(i)=\text{Probability}(i)=C/v(x_i)$, but $\int dx C/v(x)$ is not force to be 1. Of course, one may not need the concept of classical entropy at all and may simply argue $C/v(x)$ matches the high energy quantum humps. Quantum entropy still exists because the humps are caused by interference of various $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities, so there is stochasticity not present in the classical case. In a previous note, we argued that quantum entropy is $-2 \int dx Wx dW/dx + \sum_p a(p)a(-p) \ln(a(p)a(-p))$. The first term integrates to a constant regardless of W , but the second may be evaluated in the high energy limit which we do.

General Approach to Shannon's Entropy

Shannon's entropy is usually written as: $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ ((1)). This is consistent with mutually exclusive results, each with probability $P(i)$, for each possible outcome. Thus, it makes sense to write: $\sum_i P(i)=1$. For each outcome, one of the i values must result. If N is large, there are $NP(i)$ occurrences of each i result, but they can occur in any order. The \ln of the number of arrangements is:

$$\ln[N! / \text{Product} (NP(i))!] = \text{constant} - N \sum_i P(i)\ln(P(i)) \quad ((2))$$

Thus, Shannon's entropy follows. We suggest, however, that for non-mutually exclusive results, counting is performed in a different manner, yielding a different entropy than ((2)).

Classical Density and Correspondence Principle

According to the correspondence principle, one may replace quantum bound state density $W(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)=\text{wavefunction}$) with $C/v(x)$ where $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. As a result, $C/v(x)$ represents a probability for a particle to be at x , at least the way it is presented in the literature as being proportional to dt . If one argues that $C/v(x)$ simply "somewhat" matches the peaks of the high energy quantum density $W(x)W(x)$, there is no need to assume a classical probability to be at x . For the sake of argument, we pursue the idea that $C/v(x)$ is somehow related to the probability of detecting a particle at x .

Classical motion is deterministic. If one breaks a one dimensional length L into fixed dx intervals, a particle passes through each, but with different speeds. It seems probability is linked to the time the particle spends in each dx i.e. is proportional to dt (2). A fast speed means a short time and a low probability for the particle to be detected it seems. Whether a particle is detected or not in dx at x_i has nothing to with whether it is detected in dx at x_j . Thus, $P(x)$ events are not mutually exclusive as they are in the usual Shannon's entropy approach. For each

interval dx , there is a probability $C/v(x)$ for the particle to be detected and $1-C/v(x)$ probability for it not to be detected. There is no reason for $\int dx C/v(x)$ to be normalized to one.

According to (3), information is $\ln(P(x_i))$, but nowhere in the derivation is there a requirement that $\sum_i P(x_i)=1$. One simply measures the rarity of an outcome. If one performs measurements at each $dx-x_i$ pair, the two events at each x_i are detecting the particle and not detecting it. Consider N half cycles of a bound system i.e. N particle movements from one turning point to another. For interval dx at x_i , $NP(x_i)$ detections and $1-NP(x_i)$ non-detections should occur, but one does not know the order. Thus, one has the following scenarios:

$$N! / [(NP(i))! (1-NP(i))!] \quad ((3))$$

Result ((3)) holds for each i region, but the regions are not linked. Thus, one takes the product of ((3)) over all regions for the total number of arrangements. This differs from ((2)).

$$\text{Number of scenarios} = \text{Product over } i \text{ } N! / [(NP(i))! (1-NP(i))!] \quad ((4))$$

Taking \ln leads to an entropy of the form:

$$S = - \sum_i n(i) \ln(n(i)) + (1-n(i)) \ln(1-n(i)) \quad \text{where } n(i)=NP(i) \quad ((5))$$

We suggest ((5)) is the entropy which should be used to describe the classical picture, if in fact there is a classical entropy. One may have a detector which detects particles whether they move quickly or slowly.

In (2), $S = - \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ ((6)) is used as entropy and a link is made to the classical scenario. We suggest two different ideas are mixed if one uses ((6)). It seems one first considers a single particle and argues it must be at one x_i or another, in other words makes the problem one with mutually exclusive results. One then interprets $P(x_i)$ as the probability for the particle to be at x_i . We argue that $P(x_i)$ is the probability to detect a particle within dx at x_i and that the particle is guaranteed to be at x_i at t_i (the appropriate classical time). Thus, the events are not mutually exclusive and the $P(x_i)$ events are not constrained by $\sum_i P(x_i)$. It seems possible to have probabilities for different events which are not mutually exclusive and still calculate an average information. A coin and die are examples of mutually exclusive events, but detecting various types of birds within a certain area is not. There is a relative probability to detect a certain kind of bird versus another, but it is also possible to detect both during a measurement. There is no constraint $\sum_i P(i) = 1$ in such a case.

Quantum Entropy in High Energy Limit

In the literature (1), $-W^*W \ln(W^*W)$ (where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction) is often used as entropy density. In a previous note, however, we suggested:

$$\text{Entropy} = -2 \int dx W^* x dW/dx + \int dp a(p) a(-p) \ln(a(p) a(-p)) \quad ((6)) \quad (1 \text{ dimension})$$

where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. The first term on the RHS of ((6)) always integrates to the same constant regardless of the wavefunction, so we focus on the second term.

From (2), in the high energy limit, $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ (bound state) is equated to $C/v(x)$ where $\int dx C/v(x) = 1$. One may consider obtaining $P(p)$ using:

$$\int dp P(p) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \int dx KE(x) \text{ density}(x) = \int dp \frac{p^2}{2m} P(p) \quad ((7))$$

$$\int dx KE(x) C/v(x) = \int dp KE(x) C/v(x) dx/dp = \int dp KE(x) C/v(x) p/m 1/F(x)$$

So $P(p) = C/F(x)$ where one must express x in terms of p .

$$\text{Alternatively, consider } 1/F(x) dp = dt = dx/v(x) \quad ((8))$$

If one considers ((6)) with $a(p) = a(-p)$, then the high energy limit is:

$$\text{Entropy} = \int dp C/F(x) \ln(C/F(x)) = \int dx C/v(x) \ln(C/F(x)) \quad ((9))$$

Thus, one may perform an integral over x to evaluate an integral over p .

Consider an interpretation of ((9)) together with $\sum_p a(p)a(-p) \ln(a(p)a(-p))$ with $a(p) = a(-p)$ for simplicity. If $a(p)a(p)$ is almost 1 i.e. there is a strong weight for the p to occur, $a(p)a(p) \ln(a(p)a(p))$ is almost 0 because of \ln . In other words, the expected momentum means a small "rare" information (here we replace the word information with rare information). If $a(p)a(p)$ is almost 0, then $a(p)a(p) \ln(a(p)a(p))$ is again almost 0. If one knows a p does not really contribute, there is no rare information density. Thus, it seems it is the set of p 's which are neither expected or rare which account for quantum entropy. These occur because of stochasticity. In the high energy limit, matters are not so clear because $F(x)$ is used. A low $P(p)$ means a large $F(x)$, but $C/F \ln(C/F)$ goes to 0 or is small. Thus, places with high force have low rare information density. If $C/F(x) = 1$, again one has 0 rare information. It is possible there is no physical interpretation in the sense that the classical high energy limit is only an approximation to the quantum scenario of many humps. It is the humps, it seems, which contribute to the entropy with ((9)) only being an approximation.

((9)) is quite different, it seems, from: $\int dx C/v(x) \ln(C/v(x))$ used in (2) except in the case of the oscillator. According to (2), $-\int dx W(x)W(x) \ln(WW) = -\int dp a(p)a(p) \ln(a(p)a(p)) + C1$ where $C1$ is a constant involving k and m .

Consider the high energy limits:

$$-\int dx W(x)W(x) \ln(WW) = -\int dx C/\sqrt{(2m)(E-.5kxx)} \ln[C/\sqrt{(2m)(E-.5kxx)}] \quad ((10a))$$

And

$$-\int dp C/\sqrt{(2kE-kpp/m)} \ln[C/\sqrt{(2kE-kpp/m)}] \quad ((10b))$$

((10a)) and ((10b)) are of the same form with $F=-kx$.

((9)) also differs from ((5)) causing one to ask if there is any use of the latter.

Quantum entropy is based on $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ terms. These do not disappear, neither do humps in the high energy quantum limit. The quantum density $W(x)W(x)$ is not $C/v(x)$, rather $C/v(x)$ is a curve which passes through the humps. Thus, there is no reason to expect quantum entropy should represent a kind of classical entropy in the high energy limit. In fact, the humps in the high energy limit are caused by interference of different $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities at the same x point. In other words, stochasticity remains even in the high energy limit and so: $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ =Probability to be used in Shannon's entropy still seems to make sense. In the classical case, there is no such stochasticity. There is a specific momentum at each x which changes according to $-dV/dx$. We argued that in quantum mechanics, $V(x)$ =Sum over $k V(k)\exp(ikx)$. This is identical for both low and high energy suggesting stochastic hits in both cases.

This still begs the question as to whether one should even consider the idea of information for the classical case as has been done in ((5)). If a very good detector is used, it always detects a particle at each dx about x_i whether the particle is moving quickly or slowly. In such a case, there is no reason to think of dt as proportional to a density or probability(x). One may argue it is only similar to the peak value of a quantum hump in the high energy limit. For example, consider a high energy dominant term: $\int dx \quad 4\cos(p_1x)\cos(p_1x) a(p_1)a(p_1)$ from $W(x)W(x)$ (using $-/+p_1$) which may be rewritten as $\int p_1 dx \quad 4 \cos(p_1x)\cos(p_1x) a(p_1)a(p_1) / p_1$. Near a hump where p_1 dominants, $\cos(p_1x)=1$. At another hump, p_2 dominates, but one has: $\int dx \quad 4 a(p)a(p)/p$ which may explain the form $C/v(x)$. Thus, one may still have high energy quantum entropy without considering classical entropy. Nevertheless, if there is uncertainty in detecting a classical particle moving through a fixed dx because its speed is high, it seems one could consider ideas of information as done in section 1.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we formulate a classical average information based on the idea that $P(x)=C/v(x)$ i.e. if a particle is moving quickly the detector has less of a chance of detecting it. One may, however, have detectors which always detect a particle and so the idea of a classical

density may not have physical meaning. Rather, $C/v(x)$ may simply match peak values of $W(x)W(x)$ in the high energy limit. The quantum system still has entropy because it usually consists of many humps caused by the interference of different $\exp(ipx)$ values at the same x . Thus it seems there is still stochasticity which does not exist in the classical situation. In a previous note we argued that quantum entropy is: $-2 \int dx Wx dW/dx + \text{Sum over } p \ln(a(p)a(-p))$. The first term always integrates as a constant so we try to calculate the second term in the high energy limit. We give a high energy classical approximation for this entropy.

References

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